

DEPENDENCE OF INTERFACE PLY ORIENTATION ON DELAMINATION GROWTH DIRECTIONALITY AND MIGRATION

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1 Introduction

Delamination is often considered as one of the most critical failure modes in composite materials. Delaminations develop from a number of processes/features such as ply-drop-offs, impact damage, notches and manufacturing defects. Even a simple, single plane defect can result in multiplane delamination growth [1,2]. Indeed, delamination growth is often associated to secondary processes such as intralaminar or translaminar damage.

One of the most popular approaches to characterise propagation of delaminations has been the application of linear-elastic fracture mechanics which requires the quantification of the critical strain energy-release rate of the interface at which delamination grows [3]. Coupon tests have been successfully used to study the delamination fracture toughness of composites in mode I, II, III and combinations thereof. The most commonly used configurations to characterise fracture toughness for composites are double cantilever beam (DCB) [4] for mode I, 3 point and 4 point end notched flexure (3-ENF, 4-ENF) and end loaded split (ELS) for mode II and mixed-mode bending [5] (MMB) which is capable of producing an array of I-II mode mixities. These tests have been used to mainly characterise unidirectional ply interfaces. However, the use of purely unidirectional layups in structures is limited and a full characterisation of multidirectional ply interfaces is needed [6]. Furthermore, those multidirectional ply interfaces are more prone to delamination [7].

Studies which investigate the micromechanisms associated with mode II delamination have often been focused on the understanding of matrix fracture. It is generally recognised that damage initiates at the adjacent fibres and extends into the matrix through a

series of angled microcracks that develop ahead of the crack tip [8]. When these microcracks coalesce, the delamination effectively propagates directly adjacent to one of the plies at the interface. Whether it is the uppermost or lowermost ply is dictated by the orientation of the applied shear stress component [9], as shown in Fig. 1. After initiation, the behaviour of the delamination will depend on the orientation of the directing ply, i.e. the ply close to which the delamination will propagate. If the directing ply is at an orientation that matches the delamination growth direction, the delamination will continue to propagate at that ply interface. If the angle mismatch exceeds a critical value, the crack will grow through the ply, leading to a change of delamination interface. This process is illustrated in Fig. 2.

Two different mechanisms can be isolated from these observations: delamination preferentially grows along the direction of the fibres at a ply interface (*directionality*) and, if forced to grow obliquely to the fibres, a change of delamination plane typically ensues (*migration*). The objectives of the research reported in this paper are to firstly quantify the directionality of the mode II delamination toughness, and secondly to identify fractographically the micromechanisms associated with directionality.

The challenge in trying to quantify the effect of directionality on composite coupons is manifested by the consistent presence of migration when trying to characterise angled ply interfaces. A new strategy is therefore needed to understand this effect while suppressing delamination migration. In this paper, only the geometrical effect of the fibres will be studied. For this purpose the fibres and the matrix of

the composite specimen were replaced by an isotropic substrate that prevented migration.

2 Experimental studies

A replica specimen with two adhesively bonded arms was used for the tests. Such analogy has been successfully used in previous work [10,11] to explain crack tip stress distribution in mode II composite delamination. At the delaminating interface of this specimen, the texture of an idealised hexagonally packed composite interface was reproduced. The process to obtain the proposed geometries is summarised in Fig. 3. The geometry of the fibre-dominated side of a delamination (the directing ply) was taken as the start point, Fig. 3(a). The composite supporting the directing fibres was replaced by an isotropic substrate (steel) to prevent migration, Fig. 3(b). This geometry (Fig. 3(b)) proved to be difficult to machine with the CNC tools available; therefore, following extensive development, the final geometry adopted was slightly different, Fig. 3(c).

The aim of this experiment was to prove the dependence of the crack path on the surface features of the directing ply. Also, the experiment aimed to prove the independence of the crack path on the surface features of the non-directing ply. These tests will highlight the correlation between the crack path and the critical energy release rate of the delaminating interface. Also, the test would generate the failure surfaces necessary to fractographically glean the micromechanisms associated with the variation of critical strain energy release rate of the delaminating interface.

2.1 Experimental setup

The specimens for the directionality experiment were made of a mild steel, EN1A, and were CNC machined to the geometry in Fig. 3(c) taking into account the limitations of the machining tools to produce small features. The final adopted geometry is shown in Fig. 4. The grooves were machined at three different angles 90° , 0° and 45° with respect to the beam direction (Fig. 5).

The bond thickness was designed to best match the stress field at the interply resin rich layer of a composite. More details of the design process can be found in the Section 3 of this paper. The final

thickness adopted was 3 mm (Fig. 4) and specimen width was 20 mm. Specimens were tested with the fixed-ratio mixed-mode (FRMM) test (Fig. 1) to produce a mixed-mode ratio $G_{II}/G_I = 4/3$ [12] with a phase angle $\psi = \text{atan}(G_I/G_{II}) = 36.8^\circ$. This ratio was sufficient to drive the delamination to grow next to one interface [13]. A 45 mm long Teflon film insert was used as a starter crack. Arms were sandblasted before bonding with Araldite 2011 and cured at room temperature under clamping pressure with Teflon shims to control the bond thickness (Fig. 4).

Three different configurations were tested, $0^\circ/90^\circ$, $90^\circ/0^\circ$ and $45^\circ/-45^\circ$. The load conditions of the test determined which of the two arms would be the directing ply. In this case it was the upper ply, at which the load was introduced (Fig. 1). The directing ply will hereafter be identified with an underline.

3 Numerical studies

A linear elastic plane strain finite element model was created to verify the validity of approach. The model compared the stress field at the resin and the adhesive. Two areas were studied, the resin/adhesive mid-plane and the boundary between the fibres/resin and steel/adhesive (Fig. 6). The model, with the same dimensions as the experimental setup, was subjected to mixed-mode delamination conditions as summarised in Fig. 1. A refined area with 20 fibres on the length direction and 3 fibres on the width direction was embedded into a larger area with composite properties. This guaranteed that no end effects were observed on the results and that an adequate mesh refinement could be achieved in the heterogeneous region. The dimensions used for the composite model, i.e. the fibre diameter and thickness of the intralaminar resin-rich layer, were obtained from a cross-section from CFRP panels used in a larger study for delamination directionality [14]. The fibres were arranged in an idealised hexagonal packing. A parametric study was performed for the determination of the bond thickness of the replica specimen. The thicknesses considered were 0.5, 1, 2, 3 and 4.6 mm.

Fig. 7 shows the magnitude of the principal stresses at the matrix. For clarity, only the composite and two thicknesses (1 and 3 mm) are shown. The

presence of the riblets generated an oscillation in the stress field ahead of the crack tip which is not observed in the composite section. Increasing the adhesive bond thickness reduced the effect of the riblets at the mid-plane and smoothed the stress field. At the adhesive/steel interface the effect of the adhesive thickness was, as expected, not significant (Fig. 8).

4 Test results

The delamination propagated cohesively in specimens $90^\circ/0^\circ$ and $45^\circ/-45^\circ$ and adhesively in specimen $0^\circ/90^\circ$. The test was stable for the adhesive failure and unstable for the cohesive case. It was therefore possible to measure the fracture toughness except for the values of delamination onset only.

4.1 Fractographic results

The two specimens that had failed cohesively ($90^\circ/0^\circ$ and $45^\circ/-45^\circ$) exhibited cusps [9] at different angles as shown in Fig. 9. The delamination propagated predominantly at the interface adjacent to the upper arm as predicted from the shear direction (Fig. 1). It should be noted that obtaining interfaces with a directing ply of 90° and 45° is very unusual in composite materials. If the delamination is forced to grow at these ply interfaces, migration will generally occur. Micrographs of the edges and the cusps were taken with a stereo microscope (Fig. 10). However, the observations at the specimen edge have to be considered with caution. The fracture processes have a full 3D development; if a single cross section is studied it could lead into simplistic conclusions. This is also true for composite materials.

After inspecting the edges, the two arms were separated under mode I loading. The three areas of the specimen are clearly distinguishable in Fig. 9. The exposed failed surfaces were gold sputtered and examined with a Hitachi S-3700 scanning electron microscope (SEM).

4.1.1 Interface $90^\circ/0^\circ$

The delamination process was unstable and the sequence of the events could only be established by post-mortem analysis. During the test, microcracks started developing in the adhesive layer ahead of the crack tip. These microcracks were then united by a main crack which allowed the full propagation of the delamination. This was determined by the fact that

the microcrack, denoted as A-A' (Fig. 10), had an uninterrupted path. Contrarily, microcracks B-B' and C-C' were interrupted at the junction with A-A'. This suggested that A-A' occurred before B-B'.

The fracture surface was covered with large cusps that after starting at both free edges propagated transversally meeting at the centre. This created a very intricate cusp pattern as can be seen in Fig. 9(a). Close examination under the SEM revealed the presence of ribs adjacent to the riblets (Fig. 11). Ribs have been observed in composites with a thick interlaminar resin-rich layer [9] and their origin is thought to be the coalescence of the angled microcracks (A-A' in Fig. 10) with the main crack (C-C' in Fig. 10). Two areas can be distinguished, a smooth side at the right and a rough side at the left of Fig. 11. The smooth part of the rib was created during the microcracking process and the rough side with riverlines during the crack coalescence. The riverlines were used to determine the crack growth direction [9] and suggested that the microcracks could have initiated at the steel riblets.

4.1.2 Interface $45^\circ/-45^\circ$

Similarly to interface $90^\circ/0^\circ$, angled microcracks developed at the adhesive layer (Fig. 12). This time the main crack (B-B') had a continuous path and the microcrack (A-A') was stopped when meeting B-B' which suggested that microcrack A-A' occurred after the main crack B-B' originated.

The fracture surface was covered with cusps transverse to the riblets. Similarly to composites, one arm contained a majority of cusps while the other had scallops [9]. These cusps were large enough to be appreciated by the naked eye.

Macroscopic ribs were also found in the early stages of delamination growth. The ribs were at 45° with respect to the length. This suggested that the microcracks also developed at this angle following the direction of the riblets of the lower arm.

Detailed SEM analysis (Fig. 13) revealed the presence of secondary cusps parallel to the riblets. The local crack growth was inferred from the direction of the riverlines. The parallel cusps initiated at the two adjacent features and propagated

towards the middle. However, the two cracks did not meet at the middle.

It is not common to observe these kind of cusps when testing composite coupons under controlled mixed-mode conditions. It is usual, though, to find them in failure analysis of structures [9] where a mix of bending, torsion, and tension/compression loads is present. The authors have been able to consistently observe cusps with this morphology in CFRP coupons obtained from a previous study on delamination migration and directionality [14]. An example of these cusps is shown in . This micrograph was taken from a tapered width end-loaded split (ELS) specimen. The Teflon insert that was used as a starter crack can be seen at the top of the micrograph. The insert was placed at the laminate mid-plane, $45^\circ/-45^\circ$ ply interface (the directing ply changes for this load conditions). It is important to note that delamination migration occurred close to the site at which this micrograph had been taken.

4.1.3 Interface $0^\circ/90^\circ$

This configuration was the only one that exhibited pure adhesive failure. Similarly to previous specimens, the delamination initiated at the insert tip and propagated next to the upper arm. No other microcracks in the adhesive were observed other than the first one (Fig. 15). It can be seen in Fig. 9(c) that the crack returned to the mid plane when the mode I loading became dominant (during the exposure of the surfaces for inspection). This indicated that a good bond had been achieved. Therefore, the difference with specimens $90^\circ/0^\circ$ and $45^\circ/-45^\circ$ was not due to a poor bond but to different failure mechanisms associated with the direction of the riblets.

5 Discussion

Delamination has been the focus of a considerable amount of research over the last three decades. Much of this research has focused on characterising delamination over a range of mode-mixities and ply interfaces.

While the use of coupons is important to characterise fracture toughness, their application to observe and understand delamination growth at a larger scale is limited. Indeed, to reproduce in-service damage in test coupon has proven to be a

challenging task. One of the main challenges for delamination is mode III and mixed mode II/III characterisation. In these tests the delamination often migrates which invalidates the fracture toughness results.

The test proposed in this paper, although not intended for fracture toughness measurements, produced suitable fracture surfaces for the study of delamination directionality. The choice of interface was purely determined by the sense of the shear stress at the crack tip. As specimens $90^\circ/0^\circ$ and $0^\circ/90^\circ$ shared the same angled interface, one would expect the same outcome if the mechanism of delamination growth was limited to the ply interface alone. The choice of interface is also found in composites and is consistently observed across different loading conditions and geometries [1].

It has been suggested [9] that mode III could be identified through fractographic morphologies such as cusps that have developed parallel to the fibres (Fig. 14). Such considerations have never been proven due to the elusiveness of mode III in test coupons. The test presented in this paper could open a door to verify the origin of certain fractographic observations.

For example, the fact that cusps developed parallel to the riblets in the $45^\circ/-45^\circ$ specimen (Fig. 13) suggests that, for this type of cusps to have developed, migration needs to have been prevented. This, together with the fact that parallel cusps can develop in composites, indicates that there are mechanisms that can inhibit migration in structures. This may be due to the degree of constraint on the delamination in the test coupons. As has been shown in Ref. [14], a wider test specimen was able to consistently produce such cusps. These results are encouraging but are only the starting point for a future endeavour to characterise mode III delamination and migration.

7 Conclusions

A replica specimen has been developed for the study of delamination directionality. Parallels to composite materials have been drawn and the possibility of generating parallel cusps to study mode III delamination has been highlighted.

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The tests presented in this paper aim to illustrate that the mechanisms observed in these replica specimens do not differ from those that occur in composite materials.

To date, this fundamental behaviour of delamination of composite materials has been neglected in predictive models. The most widespread techniques, the cohesive method or the virtual crack closure technique, both assume that delamination propagates in an isotropic interface (i.e. both mode II and mode III critical energy release rates are the same). The tests in this paper, however, have demonstrated the different behaviour of angled interfaces and the importance of understanding its causes.

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Fig. 1 Loading conditions of a FRMM test. Detail of the principal stress direction at the mid-plane for the specific case of the fixed-ratio mixed-mode test

Fig. 2 Delamination migration mechanism [9].

Fig. 3 Schematic cross-sections of (a) the fibre-dominated side of a delaminated composite interface,

(b) the same interface considering an isotropic substrate and (c) proposed geometry for the tests.

Fig. 4 Specimen geometry with detailed riblet geometry shown.

Fig. 5 Schematic 3D view of (a) $90^\circ/0^\circ$, (b) $45^\circ/-45^\circ$ and (c) $0^\circ/90^\circ$ specimens.

Fig. 6 Zoom of the FE mesh near the crack tip of the specimen shown in Fig. 1 for (a) the composite model and (b) the replica model

Fig. 7 Normalised maximum principal stress at the mid-plane of the bondline. The displacement is normalised over a number of features.

Fig. 8 Normalised maximum principal stress at the matrix/fibre and the adhesive/steel interface.

Fig. 9 Fracture surface of (a) $90^\circ/0^\circ$ specimen (b) $45^\circ/-45^\circ$ specimen and (c) $0^\circ/90^\circ$ specimen. The upper image for each specimen corresponds to the upper arm which is the directing ply.

Fig. 10 Micrograph from the $90^\circ/0^\circ$ specimen edge. The microcrack is denoted as A-A' and the main linking cracks as B-B' and C-C'.

Fig. 11 Scanning electron micrograph of the upper matching surface of $90^\circ/0^\circ$ specimen.

Fig. 12 Micrograph from the $45^\circ/-45^\circ$ specimen edge.

Fig. 13 Scanning electron micrograph of the upper matching surface of the $45^\circ/-45^\circ$ specimen.

Fig. 14 Scanning electron micrograph of the lower matching surface of a $-45^\circ/45^\circ$ interface

Fig. 15 Micrograph from the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ specimen edge.